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Research

Verbal Action in Buddhist Literature

Phyu Phyu Thein^{*1}, *Aye Myat Thu*¹, *Mya Thuzar Hlaing*²

^{1*} Dr, Lecturer, Department of Oriental Studies, University of Mandalay, Union of Myanmar

¹ Ms., Lecturer, Department of Oriental Studies, Maubin University, Union of Myanmar

² Dr, Assistant Lecturer, Department of Oriental Studies, University of Mandalay, Union of Myanmar

* *Corresponding author*

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Abstract: This paper is about the nature of good and bad conducts in verbally, their consequences and the factors of four verbal misconducts. This paper points out that the fruitful words can give the secular and in secular benefit in both present and future existences. These benefits can also be got the listeners too. Therefore, in order to describe the nature and consequences of verbal good conducts and bad conducts and to apply the verbal good conducts for establishing the peaceful social relationship, this paper is presented. This paper is presented by using destructive method and extracted from Pāli texts, commentaries, sub-commentaries and their texts.

Keywords : verbal, abstaining, action, word

Introduction

Buddhist people believe that there is action and reaction in the world. The word action is used in Pāli as “*kamma*”. There are three of action in bodily (*kāyakkamma*) action verbally (*vacīkkamma*) and action in mentally (*manokamma*). A good deed in bodily, verbally and mentally is called wholesome deed (*kusalakkamma*) while a bad deed in bodily, verbally and mentally is called unwholesome deed (*akusalakkamma*). And then, verbal conducts will be presented in this paper. A good word is very important for building a pleasant society. Therefore in order to build social relationship by four verbal good conducts, this paper will be presented by describing the nature the consequences and the factors of the four verbal good and bad conduct.

Good Verbal Actions

There are four kinds of good verbal actions in Buddhist Literature. They are:

1. *Musāvāda Viratī Sucarita* (Abstaining from telling lies)
2. *Pisuṇavācā Viratī Sucarita* (Abstaining from slandering)
3. *Pharusavācā Viratī Sucarita* (Abstaining from speaking harsh words)
4. *Samhappalāpavācā Viratī Sucarita* (Abstaining from speaking vain words)

***Musāvāda Viratī Sucarita* (Abstaining from Telling Lies)**

Musāvāda Viratī Sucarita means abstaining from telling lies. Lying to others by word, letter or gesture is a *musāvāda ducātita*.¹ Lying done by word of mouth is called evil verbal conduct (*vacīducarita*).²

Benefits of *Musāvāda Viratī Sucarita* – One who refrains from telling lies will reach a good destination. Moreover, one will enjoy the following benefits:- clear pronunciation, even teeth, sweet smelling breath, a well-built physique, good eyesight and hearing, good features and fair complexion, influence on others, effective speech and calmness of mind.³

The following story⁴ illustrates the benefit of telling truth. Once upon a time there lived a hermit in a garden. A friend *Upasakā* came to the hermit with his wife and a small son. While they were talking, the son was bitten by a poisonous snake and he was unconscious. The parents brought the child to the hermit and entreated him to save their child. The hermit took a solemn vow and said words of truth as, “I have been a hermit for over 50 years. While in this holy life, I practiced *Dhamma* only for seven days. The remaining days and years I felt lazy and unhappy. If my asseveration of truth is true, may this child be free from poisonous effect now.” After the words of truth had been said, the child could be able to open his eyes a little bit and murmured words of mother. The poison shifted from the upper part of the chest downwards. The father took a solemn vow and said words of truth, “I always hate to give offerings. I totally hate the act of giving. When beggars and almsmen came to my house, I offer something to them although I do not love giving. I follow only traditional custom. If my asseveration of truth is true, may my son be free from poisonous effect.” After saying these words of truth the poison shifted from waist downwards. So the child rose up and sat silently by now.

The mother, in order to save the child’s life spoke a vow like this: “Oh my only beloved son, I totally hate both your father and the poisonous snake. I totally despise both equally. Although I do not love your father, I continued to live with him in accordance with the wishes of my relatives to avoid shame. I have to practice patience in living with your

¹ Pāḷi Myanmar Dictionary, 308.

² Paraloka Hnint Kan Sait Swan In, 226.

³ Itivuttaka Aṭṭhakathā, 224.

⁴ Jātaka Aṭṭhakathā IV, 30-6.

father. If my words are true, may you be safe from harm and suffering now.” As soon as these words were spoken all the effects of the poison in the child’s body totally disappeared. This story illustrates the immediate benefit of truthful vows.

Pisuṇavācā Viratī Sucarita (Abstaining from Slandering)

Pisuṇavācā Viratī means abstaining from slandering.⁵ Slandering means talking ill to the two person with the intention of causing a chasm between the two persons who are on good friendly terms at the moment. Talking what is not true with malicious intention to cause quarrel, animosity or disagreement between the two good friends or to win over someone is *pisunvāsā*.⁶

Benefits of *Pisuṇavācā Viratī Sucarita* – One who abstains from slandering to cause disunity between the two friends on good terms will enjoy the following benefits:- never dying at the hands of others, having wealth and followers, no loss of faith in the *Dhamma* of the virtuous, no loss of friends and relatives, being loved by people, being free from wicked mentality and free from a troubled and restless mind.⁷

As the Buddha abstained from slandering to cause disunity between two good friends in every life in *Samsāra*, he was possessed of two characteristics of the body, namely, *Cattālīsadantatā* and *Aviraḷadantatā*. *Cattālīsadantatā* means the possession of 40 perfect teeth. Ordinary human beings have only 32 teeth. The Buddha has the distinctive mark of the teeth numbering exactly forty. *Aviraḷadantatā* means having forty teeth perfectly set teeth without crevices between them. For ordinary people, some have their teeth with crevices between them. In eating meat bits of meat are left stuck in the crevices. But the Buddha’s teeth are regular and even. The teeth touch each other evenly without leaving crevices between adjoining teeth. This bodily a characteristic is called *Aviraḷadantatā*.⁸

Pharusavācā Viratī Sucarita (Abstaining from Speaking Harsh Words)

Pharusavācā viratī means abstaining from speaking harsh words. Unpleasant words to the listener, miserable words, abusive words, and words used in curses are all *pharusavācā*.

Benefits of *Pharusavācā Viratī Sucarita* - One who refrains from speaking harsh words will enjoy the following benefits:- being loved by human beings, delighting human beings and

⁵ Pāḷi Myanmar Dictionary, 674.

⁶ Paraloka Hnint Kan Sait Swan In, 234-5.

⁷ Cariyāpīṭaka Aṭṭhakathā, 302.

⁸ Dīgha Nikāya Mahāvagga Aṭṭhakathā, 41.

making them appreciate him, ability to live in peace and happiness, saying pleasant words to others, being praised by many and possession of a pleasant voice with eight fine qualities.⁹

Moreover, the *Bodhisatta* avoided speaking harsh words but spoke pleasant and sweet words in the past existences while he was fulfilling *pāramīs*. Therefore the *Bodhisatta* was reborn in the celestial abode and enjoyed longer life span and five physical features, eight fine qualities of the voice.* After passing away from celestial life, he became a Buddha in human world and came to possess two characteristic features called *Pahūtajivhatā* and *Brahmassaratā*.

Pahūtajivhatā means the mark of possession of a long, tender, wide and reddish tongue. Ordinary people have thick tongue, small tongue, short and coarse tongue. But the Buddha has a long, tender, wide and reddish tongue. The tongue can be rolled like paper and put it in the nostril. The tongue can lick the ears and the nose. The tongue can cover the forehead. This excellent quality of the tongue is called *Pahūtajivhatā*.

Brahmassaratā means the characteristic mark of possession of a sublime and pleasant voice like that of a *Brahmā* King. Some people have hoarse, interrupted voice. Some have small voice. Some have short and coarse voice. Some have unpleasant voice like that of crows. The voice of the Buddha is as pleasant as that of *Brahmā* King. The voice of the *Brahmā* King is free from the defects of phlegm and bile. The voice that issues from the Buddha's mouth is very clean and so it possesses eight fine qualities. It is clear, pleasant, intelligible, pleasing to the ear, cohesive, not going beyond the audience, deep and resonant. Because of possession of such an excellent voice this characteristic mark is called *Brahmassaratā*.¹⁰

The above mentioned evidences show the benefits of abstaining from talking abusive and harsh words. So, one should refrain from speaking abusive and harsh words.

Samhappalāpavācā Viratī Sucarita (Abstaining from Speaking Vain Words)

Samhappalāpavācā viratī means abstaining from speaking vain words.¹¹ Words which are time wasting, unprofitable or detrimental to economy constitute *samhappalāpavācā*.¹²

⁹ Cariyāpiṭaka Aṭṭhakathā, 302.

* clearness, easy to understand, a melodious sound, pleasant sound, united sound, mysterious sound, echoes, no disorder. Dīgha Nikāya Mahāvagga, 171; Dīgha Nikāya Mahāvagga Aṭṭhakathā, 233.

¹⁰ Dīgha Nikāya Mahāvagga Aṭṭhakathā, 41-2.

¹¹ Pāli Myanmar Dictionary, 1002.

¹² Paraloka Hnint Kan Sait Swan In, 237.

Benefits of *Samphappalāpavācā Sucarita* - One who abstains from speaking vain talks will enjoy the following benefits:- being trusted by others, being respected by others, winning the affection of people, capable of speaking to invoke trust in him, having power, authority and influence on others, and ability to solve problems for being endowed with wisdom.¹³

As the Buddha abstained from speaking unprofitable words, he came to possess the characteristic feature called *Sīhahanutā* when he became the Buddha. *Sīhahanutālakkhaṇā* is the possession of a well-developed jaw like that of a lion. It resembles the shape of the moon shining on the twelfth waxing night of the month.¹⁴

Therefore according to the examples shown previously, one should avoid speaking vain talks but speak words which are related to mundane and supramundane affairs. We should not speak words which are unprofitable to social and economic affairs and also unprofitable for the supramundane affairs. It is better to remain silent.

Bad Verbal Actions

There are four kinds of bad verbal actions in Buddhist Literature. They are:

1. *Musāvāda Ducarita* (Telling Lies)
2. *Pisuṇavācā Ducarita* (Slandering)
3. *Pharusavācā Ducarita* (Speaking Harsh Words)
4. *Samphappalāpavācā Ducarita* (Speaking Vain Words)

***Musāvāda Ducarita* (Telling Lies)**

The intention at the time of lying to others by word, letter or gesture to cause false impression is called *musāvāda*.¹⁵ As this action is done mostly by word of mouth, it is called *musāvāda*.¹⁶ The categories of *musāvāda kamma* are failure to keep promise, breaking one's word, failure to keep the appointment, cheating others, pretention to be a man of honour, speaking and acting to impress others.

Factors of *Musāvāda Ducarita* – There are four factors which decide whether a *musāvāda kammamāthā* is accomplished or not. The four factors are: (1) The statement is not true. (2) There is an intention to lie. (3) It is actually spoken. (4) Other understands what has been spoken. If these four factors are present the offence of telling lies is accomplished. If one of these four factors is absent, the offence of telling lies is not accomplished.¹⁷ For monks it

¹³ Cariyāpiṭaka Aṭṭhakathā, 302.

¹⁴ Dīgha Nikāya Mahāvagga Aṭṭhakathā, 41.

¹⁵ Khuddaka Nikāya, Vimānavatthu Aṭṭhakathā, 97-9.

¹⁶ Paraloka Hnint Kan Sait Swan In, 234-5.

¹⁷ Saṅgahabhāsā Ṭīkā, 373.

incurs *Pacittiya āpatti* if the two factors are present - 1. the intention to lie and 2. actual telling lies.

Evil Consequences of *Musāvāda Ducarita* - Telling lies with malicious intent can lead one to *apāyas* – miserable abodes. Telling lies in mockery, telling lies to prevent one’s children from going to festivities are not grave offences. Telling lies causing little destruction to property is a minor offence. The offence is given when the destruction is large. If the economic ruin is equal, the offence is greater to cause ruin to a man of morality. The offence is smaller to cause ruin to a man of deficient morality.¹⁸

The evil benefits that can be encountered by telling lies with malicious intent are shown in *Pañcaka*¹⁹, *Aṭṭhaka*²⁰, and *Navaka Nipātas*²¹ in *Aṅguttara Nikāya*. One who tells lies with malicious intention will be reborn in one of the lower, miserable abodes, namely, hell, animal world, *Peta* world and the world of *Asūras*. When he is freed from the *apāyas* and is reborn in human world he can be falsely accused. There will be many enemies. He will physically and mentally suffer. He can be punished, imprisoned and expelled from one’s country. The evil benefits of telling lies are shown in *Itivuttaka Aṭṭhakathā*²² as follows: (1) poor pronunciation, (2) uneven teeth, (3) foul breath, (4) unhealthy complexion, (5) poor eyesight and poor hearing, (6) defective appearance, (7) lack of influence on others, (8) harshness of speech, and (9) restlessness of the mind.

As the saying goes, “Lying begins from Cetiya”, the evil benefits of a liar are shown in the story of King Cetiya.²³

At the beginning of the world, the word of King Cetiya called Uparava of Sotthiya city in Cetiya Kingdom is the first lie. King Cetiya was not an ordinary king. He was endowed with four powers, namely, ability to fly through the sky, being guarded by devas, fragrance of sandalwood from his body, and the scent of brown lotus from his mouth. While Cetiya was a student at the Taxila, he became friends with Korakalamba, the younger brother of Kapila, the Great Parohita. Cetiya gave his promise to appoint him in the position of Royal Parohita when he became a king. When Cetiya became a king, he could not deprive the old Parohita of his post. The old Parohita relinquished his post and became a hermit. But the position of Parohita was only concerned with the elder brother. The younger brother was not

¹⁸ Abhidhamma Piṭaka, Aṭṭhasālinī Aṭṭhakathā, 141.

¹⁹ Aṅguttara Nikāya, Pañcaka Choka Sattaks Nipāta, 259.

²⁰ Aṅguttara Nikāya, Aṭṭhaka Navaka Dasaka Ekādasaka Nipāta, 154.

²¹ Aṅguttara Nikāya, Aṭṭhaka Navaka Dasaka Ekādasaka Nipāta, 178.

²² Itivuttaka Aṭṭhakathā, 224.

²³ Jātaka Aṭṭhakathā III, 431.

entitled to it. Therefore King Cetiya told lies that Korakalamba was the elder and Kapila the younger in order to appoint Korakalamba in the position of Prohita. When King Cetiya told lies, the king's four great powers suddenly disappeared. Then the hermit admonished the king by showing his offence. The king told lies for the second without obeying the admonition of the hermit. As soon as he spoke lies for the second time his feet sunk into for the second time his feet sunk into the earth to the ankle. When the king spoke lies for the third time he sank into the earth knee-deep. When the king lied for the fourth time he was sunk to navel deep. When the king lied for the sixth time he was sunk to the breast level. When the king lied for the seventh time, the earth went asunder issuing flames and fumes. The king was borne down to the nethermost hell, *Avīci*. When Cetiya king spoke lies, it was the time when there was no one who told lies. All were established at truthfulness. At the time when truthfulness was firmly established, telling lies was a very distinctive and very grave offence. Not to mention the ordinary people, King Cetiya who was endowed with four great powers immediately fell to *Avīci* hell.

The Buddha preached in *Dukanipāta* in *Aṅguttara Nikāya*²⁴ as: “Although *Kinnarās* and *Kinnarās* are able to speak human language, they avoid speaking human language with two objectives of not telling lies and not accusing others with falsehood.” As the *kinnarās* and *kinnarās* that are animals are able to guard the *musāvāda kamma* securely, the intelligent wise persons are preached to abstain from committing *musāvāda kamma* by speaking truths.

***Pisuṇvācā Ducarita* (Slandering)**

Pisuṇvācā is talking ill of one person to another person in order to make him love him²⁵ or backbiting.²⁶ It means backbiting to cause disruption between two friendly persons, and telling things to cause animosity between the two friends. Attempting to win love by slandering the other is *Pisuṇvācā*. Causing disruption by gesture or by letter is also *Pisuṇvācā*. As the *Pisuṇvācā* is mostly a verbal action, it is included in *vaciducārita*.²⁷

Factors of *Pisuṇvācā Ducarita* - There are four factors by which the accomplishment of *Pisuṇvācā kammāpatha* is decided. The four factors are:- (1) There are two persons who are on friendly terms. (2) One has the intention of causing a chasm between them and winning their love. (3) One makes the effort to cause a chasm. (4) The two persons understand what has been spoken. Although the four factors are present, and if the friendship is not broken, it

²⁴ No. 61 of *Puggala Vagga*. *Aṅguttara Nikāya*, Ekaka Duka Tika Catuka Nipāta, 77.

²⁵ *Vibhāvinī*, 373-4.

²⁶ *Pāli Myanmar Dictionary*, 674.

²⁷ *Paraloka Hnint Kan Sait Swan In*, 234-5.

does not accomplish *kamma* but it is only a misdeed. If friendship is broken, it achieves *kamma*.²⁸

Evil Benefits of *Pisuṇvācā Ducarita* - The gravity of the *Pisuṇvācā* offence varies according to the morality and virtue of the persons whose friendship is broken. If the person who is slandered is moral and virtuous, the offence is grave. If the person who is slandered is immoral and unvirtuous, the offence is light.²⁹

Those who commit the offence of slandering are reborn in one of the four *Apāyas* called hell, the world of animals, the world of *Petas* and the world of *Asūras*. After suffering in *Apāyas* for many years, they may be reborn in human world. Then they will be separated from their relatives and friends. The evil consequences of committing slander are shown in *Cariya Piṭaka Aṭṭhakathā* as follows:- dying at the hands of others, having few friends and followers, losing confidence in the *dhamma* of the virtuous, having to part from the beloved ones, lack of permanent friendship, and having a troubled and restless mind.

Evil consequences of slandering can be known by observing the example of *Sūkarapeta Vatthu*.³⁰

During the life time of Kassapa Buddha the two moral and virtuous *Theras* were residing at a small village monastery cordially and harmoniously. One day a wicked preaching monk came to this monastery. On the second day, *Dhammakathika* was taken on an alms round in the village. Because of the good faith, and generosity of the villages and wanting the shady monastery, the *Dhammakathika* began to talk slandering words against two friendly *Theras*. When slandering was repeated, the two friends were disunited. Therefore they took their alms-bowls and robes and went away to different destinations. The *Dhamma* preaching monk who caused to break up the friendship of the two monks had to suffer in hell for many years. During the life time of the Gotama Buddha the sinner monk became a *Peta* at *Gijjhakūṭa* Hill near Rājagaha. The *Peta* had a human body and a pig-head with a tail in the mouth. As the worms were continuously coming out of the mouth, the *Peta* was suffering a great deal. This story shows the dire consequence of committing slander between the two good cordial friends.

***Pharusavācā Ducarita* (Speaking Harsh Words)**

²⁸ Abhidhamma Piṭaka, Aṭṭhasālinī Aṭṭhakathā I, 142.

²⁹ Abhidhamma Piṭaka, Aṭṭhasālinī Aṭṭhakathā, 142.

³⁰ Khuddaka Nikāya, Dhammapada Aṭṭhakathā. II, 258-62.

Pharusavācā means harsh words.³¹ Harsh word means cursing oneself or others using obscene words and hurling imprecations or curses.³² Words which are unpleasant to the hearer and words used in cursing are *pharusavācās*. Regarding to cursing, there are ten kinds.* Those who want to refrain from speaking harsh words must also avoid the ten kinds of cursing.

Factors of *Pharusavācā Ducarita* - There are three factors which decide whether *Pharusavācā kamma* is accomplished or not. The three factors are: (1) someone is abused with harsh speech; (2) the speaker is angry; (3) the speaker uses harsh speech. If all these factors are present, the offence of *kamma* is accomplished. If one of the factors is absent, *kamma* is not accomplished.³³

Four Kinds of *Pharusavācā* – Regarding to speaking harsh speech, there are four different kinds. They are: (1) the words are harsh but the intention is not harsh; (2) the intention is harsh but the words are not harsh; (3) the words as well as the intention are harsh; and (4) the words as well as the intention are not harsh.³⁴

Out of the four kinds, No.1 is the kind of speech that is most commonly spoken. The harsh words spoken by parents to children, by teachers to pupils, by elder brothers and sisters to younger brothers and sisters in admonition do not amount to harsh speech as no bad intention is involved.³⁵ Only when there is bad intention in speaking harsh words, it can be called harsh speech. But if there is anger in scolding, it amounts to *kamma* as the three factors of *pharusavācā* are all present. It is considered that it incurs offence.³⁶ As to No.1, it is difficult to decide whether there is offence or not because it is concerned with innate nature. In No.2, the word is very subtle. Although the King may speak gently, “Let him sleep

³¹ Pāli Myanmar Dictionary, 694.

³² Abhidhamma Piṭaka, Aṭṭhasālinī Aṭṭhakathā I, 142.

* cursing by calling such as beggar, witch, etc.,
cursing by calling names such as thief, vagrant, etc.,
cursing by calling names such as Koliya lineage, Bharadvaja lineage, etc.,
cursing by calling names such as excreta collector, cobbler, etc.,
cursing by calling names such as leper, etc.,
cursing by calling names such as weaver of reed wall, potter, etc.,
cursing by calling names such as the long, the dwarf, etc.,
cursing by calling names such as sex-maniac, anger-pot, etc.,
cursing by calling names such as Pārajika sinner, etc., and
cursing by calling names such as dog, ox, etc.

³³ Abhidhamma Piṭaka, Aṭṭhasālinī Aṭṭhakathā I, 143.

³⁴ Aṭṭhasālinībhāsā Tīkā. II, 211.

³⁵ Abhidhamma Piṭaka, Aṭṭhasālinī Aṭṭhakathā I, 143.

³⁶ Sīlakkhandhavagga Abhinava Tīkā. 341.

in peace” in giving the order to kill a criminal, his speech is “*Pharusavācā*” because here the king had a bad intention behind these words.³⁷

Evil Consequences of *Pharusavācā Ducarita* - Those who commit the offence of *pharusavācā* are reborn in the four *Apāyas* called hell, animal world, the world of *Petas* and the world of *Asūras*. If they are reborn in the world of human beings after suffering in the *Apāyas* abodes for many years, there will be many people who do not want to listen to his voice as shown in *Aṭṭhaka Nipāta* of *Aṅguttara Nikāya*³⁸. Moreover, the evil consequences of *pharusavācā* are shown in *Dasaka Nipāta* of the same *Nikāya*³⁹ as follows:- (1) inaccessible to wealth which one should not have, (2) tarnishing of virtuous *dhammas* in one’s mind, (3) decline of one’s acquired wealth, (4) loss of faith in virtuous *dhammas*, (5) loss of delight in noble practice, (6) inflicted with punishment, (7) being afflicted with bad disease, (8) mental derangement, (9) death in bewilderment, and felling to the abodes of *Apāya* after death.

That even animals do not like harsh speech is illustrated by *Nandivīsāla Jātaka*. Once upon a time the *Bodhisatta* of Gotama Buddha was born as a bull in one existence. The bull was named Nandivīsāla. The owner Brahmin believed the strength of his bull. One day the owner Brahmin made a wager with a rich Brahmin to see whether his bull could pull the full weight of 100 loaded carts. The bet amounted to one thousand silver rupees. The owner Brahmin stayed at the head of the cart and commanded the bull to pull the carts by speaking abusively and by beating him with a goad. The *Bodhisatta* on hearing the rude words of command stopped pulling the carts. Therefore the owner lost one thousand silver rupees. The owner Brahmin made a wager with the same rich Brahmin. The bet was doubled this time. This time, the Brahmin avoided using rude words and spoke sweetly to the bull. *Nandivīsāla* Bull successively pulled a hundred fully loaded carts to the winning post. In this way the bull owner won the bet and got back the sum of two thousand silver rupees.

According to this story not to mention human being, even animals do not like rude and abusive words. People like polite and sweet speech. One does not like rude and abusive speech. In the same way others do not like rude and abusive speech. Therefore one should avoid speaking rude and abusive words.

***Samphappalāpavācā Ducarita* (Speaking Vain Words)**

³⁷ Abhidhamma Piṭaka, Aṭṭhasālinī Aṭṭhakathā I, 143.

³⁸ Aṅguttara Nikāya, Aṭṭhaka Navaka Dasaka Ekādasaka Nipāta Pāli, 78.

³⁹ *Ibid*, 393.

Samphappalāpavācā means frivolous talk that is not beneficial to oneself as well as to others.⁴⁰ Frivolous talk means saying some stories such as King Rāma's queen named Sītādevi was taken away by the great ogre, Dassagīri; or the golden rabbit and the golden tiger went to the forest to reap thatch. Because these stories have not really occurred in the past and they are created by some story-tellers in order to increase lust, anger and delusion in others, they have no essence just as chaff has no grain. They are called *samphappalāpavācā*.⁴¹ On the other hand, if such stories are told to illustrate certain points in preaching a discourse or in admonishing others it cannot be said that one commits *samphappalāpavācā*. Words are spoken or written with bad intention are also called *samphappalāpavācā*.⁴²

Factors of *Samphappalāpavācā Ducarita* - There are two factors which decide whether *kammapatha* is accomplished or not. They are:- (1) having the intention to speak vain talk, and (2) speaking vain talk.⁴³

Evil Consequences of *Samphappalāpavācā Ducarita* - Speaking vain talk is not beneficial in the present life but also one will be reborn in the four woeful abodes after his death. Even when he is liberated from there and regains human existence, there will be no one who believes his spoken words as shown in *Aṭṭhaka Nipāta* of *Āṅguttara Nikāya*.⁴⁴ Those who speak vain talks are described in *Cariya Piṭaka Aṭṭhakathā*⁴⁵ that they will suffer the following evil consequences:- (1) dislike by others, (2) without winning others' affection, (3) without winning others' respect, (4) lack of power, authority, and influence on others, (5) inability to solve problems due to poor intelligence.

Regarding to speaking vain talks, it is illustrated with the story of the dancers in *Salāyatana Vagga* in *Mahavagga Aṭṭhakathā*.⁴⁶ The dancers came into the midst of the people and talked fruitless words to cause anger and delusion. They sang songs and danced to entertain the people. When they died they had to suffer in *Pahāsa* Hell. *Pahāsa* Hell is not a separate hell. It exists at a certain place in *Avīci* Hell.

According to the preaching of the Buddha, the dancers who talked words in their entertainments reached hell when they were dead. Not only the dancers but also other people

⁴⁰ Pāli-thet Myanmar Vohāra Abhidhān, 1002.

⁴¹ Abhidhamma Piṭaka, Aṭṭhasālinī Aṭṭhakathā I, 143.

⁴² Para Loka Hinit Kan Sait Swan In, 237.

⁴³ Abhidhamma Piṭaka, Aṭṭhasālinī Aṭṭhakathā I, 143.

⁴⁴ Āṅguttara Nikāya, Aṭṭhaka Navaka Dasaka Ekādasaka Nipāta Pāli, 78.

⁴⁵ Cariyāpiṭaka Aṭṭhakathā, 302.

⁴⁶ Saṃyutta Nikāya, Salāyatanavagga Mahāvagga Saṃyutta Aṭṭhakathā, 141.

who are not dancers can be destined to hells. Therefore one must speak speeches which are beneficial to oneself and to others.

Conclusion

Through this paper, it can be known about the nature and consequences of verbal good conducts and bad conducts. To sum up it is necessary to apply correctly the four verbal actions; *musāvāda veramaṇi* (speaking only truths), *pisuṇavācā veramaṇi* (unity), *pharusavācā veramaṇi* (polite speech) and *samphappalāpā veramaṇi* (speaking only fruitful) words. A good speaking by using the four verbal actions can help to get much knowledge and to have good relationship. The Buddha advised to do verbal good conducts for getting a good relationship and for having unity. Therefore it can be assumed that these verbal good conducts should be applied by any religion in their daily life.

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Dr. Phyu Phyu Thein

Lecturer from Department of Oriental Studies, University of Mandalay, Union of Myanmar

She passed matriculation from BEHS (16), Mandalay, Myanmar. She completed her BA (Hons:), MA and MRes (Oriental Studies) from University of Mandalay on 2003, 2005 and 2006 respectively. She got PhD Degree from (University of Mandalay) on 2014. Her research preference areas are Buddhist Philosophy, Buddhist Art and Architecture, Sanskrit Language, Buddhist Culture and History of Buddhism etc.

Ms. Aye Myat Thu

Lecturer from Department of Oriental Studies, Maubin University, Union of Myanmar

She passed matriculation from BEHS (2), Nyaung Done, Patheingyi, Myanmar. She completed her BA (Hons:) and MA (Oriental Studies) from University of Yangon on 2002 and 2004 respectively. Now she is a PhD candidate at University of Mandalay. Her research preference areas are Pāli Language & Literature, Buddhist Philosophy, Buddhist Art and Architecture, Buddhist Culture and History of Buddhism etc.

Dr. Mya Thuzar Hlaing

Assistant Lecturer from Department of Oriental Studies, University of Mandalay, Union of Myanmar

She passed matriculation from BEHS (Kabyu), Kyaukpadaung, Myanmar. She completed her BA, MA and MRes (Oriental Studies) from Meiktila University on 2005, 2009 and 2010 respectively. She got PhD Degree from (University of Mandalay) on 2018. Her research preference areas are History of Buddhism, Buddhist Art and Architecture, Pāli Language & Literature, Indian Philosophy and Buddhist Culture etc.

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